

MY RULE'S ON PI NOTATION

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1.1 INTRODUCTION

If you're familiar with pi notation you will see that if $k=1$ it will be Always $n!$ Because you will multiply all the numbers from 1 to n

EXAMPEL:

$$\prod_{k=1}^{10} = 1.2.3.4.5.6.7.8.9.10 = 10!$$

1.2 goal:

The main purpose of these rules is to simplify some pi notation equations without using other long rules And understand how pi notation is related to factorials.

1.3 What if k Equals to anything but 1

Well, if you think about it k doesn't need to equal 1 but it must start from 1.

If you subtract 1 from k and then you put the number on the equation the result will be n minus that number and then factorial like this:

$$\prod_{k=0}^n k - \lambda = (n - \lambda)!$$

$$\lambda = k - 1$$

1.4 PROOF

Well, it doesn't Really need Algebraic proof It's clear but if I give you an example you will understand right away.

EXAMPEL:

$$\prod_{k=25}^{35} k - 24 = 1.2.3.4.5.6.7.8.9.10.11$$

1.5 DOES IT WORK ON Everything?

The Answer is no, there are 4 situations that the rule doesn't work on

-1 it doesn't work if k has an exponential on the equation, it only works on the other rule

-2 n needs to be less than infinity $n < \infty$

-3 it doesn't work on imaginary numbers

-4 of course n needs to be bigger or equal to k ($n \geq k$) but other than that it works on any integer number.

1.6 problems:

$$\prod_{k=-3}^{10} k - (-3) =$$

$$\prod_{k=6}^{100} k - 5 =$$

$$\prod_{k=5}^{15} k - 4 =$$

$$\prod_{k=66}^{200} k - 65 =$$

2.0 SECOND RULE

Well, it's basically the same rule but with more detail's

$$\prod_{k=0}^n (k - \lambda)^a = ((n - \lambda)!)^a$$

2.1 proof

The proof here is harder to understand but it's still pretty clear

Now we all know that $\prod_{k=0}^n (k - \lambda) = (n - \lambda)!$ if you just multiply the pi notation by itself you will get the answer right away

$$\prod_{k=0}^n (k - \lambda)^2 = \prod_{k=0}^n (k - \lambda) \cdot \prod_{k=0}^n (k - \lambda) = (n - \lambda)! (n - \lambda)! = ((n - \lambda)!)^2$$

EXAMPEL:

$$\prod_{k=3}^5 (k-2)^2 = (3!)^2 = 36$$

2.2 problems

$$\prod_{k=5}^{15} (k-4)^2 =$$

$$\prod_{k=2}^7 (k-1)^3 =$$

$$\prod_{k=5}^{15} (k-4)^3 =$$

3.0 FUNCTIONS:

3.1 first one

As you can see it's basically a factorial

3.2 second function:

This function depends on the value of Lambda.

Thank you for seeing the paper, sincerely
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